

ENGLISH VOCABULARY LEARNING OF STUDENTS IN HO CHI MINH CITY UNIVERSITY OF FOOD INDUSTRY (HUFI) REALITY AND SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

Vocabulary can be considered the most central to English language learning because without sufficient vocabulary English learners cannot understand or convey their own ideas. To learn vocabulary effectively, the English learners always apply the different ways such as methods, motivation, means and so on to achieve their goals. However, there have been many problems in learning English vocabulary of students in general and students at hufi in particular. As a result, the hufi students need to change the way as well as the point of view of English vocabulary learning.

Key words: English, vocabulary, learning, learner.

1 INTRODUCTION

The English learners have been aware of the importance of learning vocabulary. If they own a lot of vocabulary, communication, writing and listening may be easier. A well-known English linguist D.A Wilkins (1972) wrote that “without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed”. So learning English vocabulary is compulsory. In the scope of the paper, the “quantity” and the “quality” of the English vocabulary of hufi learners is mentioned as well as how to improve it. A learner’s vocabulary of English is all the words of English that the learner knows. This vocabulary has a great influence on the learner’s progress in English learning and shapes his/her communicative success in English. Despite this fact, English vocabulary can pay only a little attention from hufi learners of English in reality. Consequently, English vocabulary has been inadequately taught and learnt in hufi. Thus, there is no wonder why hufi learners of English have long suffered from incompetence in communicating in English. It is high time to attempt to find effective solutions to this situation.

2 THE REALITY OF ENGLISH VOCABULARY LEARNING OF STUDENTS IN HUFI

The part of vocabulary in language learning of students in hufi has somehow been applied to the center of the so called “traditional method” which is more of the grammar-translation method and the audiolingualism than of the communicative approach. Students usually learn English vocabulary by memorizing words in relation to the equivalents of these words in Vietnamese, mainly based on the written forms of the words. Little attention is paid to the pronunciation and its usage. An inadequate amount of actual use of the words is presented. Another thing is that the

lack of practice also contributes to poor communicative competence and performance. These facts have set such problems which hufi learners have faced as follows.

Word Choice

The link between the words in English and their Vietnamese equivalents inside students' mind is so strong that it becomes a means by which the choice of word is selected no matter how suitable the word is. This is to say, the choice of the English word bases mostly on the particularly isolated equivalent that has been personally matched in the learner's memory.

Students learn the modal "can" and "may" by means of setting up a link to the equivalents of these words in Vietnamese. But the learner may have the same Vietnamese equivalent "có thể", for these two modals. This fact results in problems like this:

Don't play football in the rain. You can have a cold.

In this example, a confusion about the use of "can" and "may" occurs. Here, a possibility of the action of "having a cold" is implied, not an ability to do this action. This is to say, "may" must be employed in this case.

Similarly, when well-linked the English verb "know" and its Vietnamese equivalent "biết" can create another case of the point.

I have never driven any sort of car because I don't know drive.

Low Access

More attention is paid to communicative competence than to communicative performance. When they receive a message in English, they can understand it completely. But when they want to express what they think in English, they encounter a nuisance of calling out the English words from their memory. This interrupts and sometimes breaks the process of thinking and also the continuity of the delivery of the speech.

Word recognition

Because of the difference in the way the learner pronounces words in English and the way native speakers of English do this, sometimes learners do not recognize the English words though they know these words in the written form.

Word pronunciation

The habit of not pronouncing word-final sounds of English learners prevents them from forming a new habit of saying word-final sounds when speaking English. Moreover, some English sounds such as /tʃ/ and /dʒ/ are totally new or strange to learner's experience. There are no equivalent sounds in Vietnamese. All these factors lead to the reality of bad pronunciation of English words among hufi learners. As a result, in speaking poor pronunciation causes potential misunderstanding or discomfort both of which may deteriorate most of a speaker's effort irrespective of the good vocabulary and the advanced grammar employed.

Word context

Many learners learn English words just in separation. Little attention to idioms, collocations and expressions are paid. At least learners should know the common expressions and collocations containing the words. Furthermore, even advanced learners give little thought to connotations and cultural associations which can serve as a key to success in cross-culture communication.

2 THE SOLUTION TO THE SITUATION

Some suggestions for situation of learning English vocabulary of hufi students are marked as follows

1. Learners should be made fully aware of the concept of “knowing a word”

Many learners think that knowing a word means knowing its meaning, spelling and pronunciation. The concept of “knowing a word” includes so much more. According to Michael McCarthy, Felicity O’Dell and Ellen Shaw (1997), knowing a new word means as follows

“It is not enough just to know the meaning of a word. You also need to know:

- a. which word is usually associated with
- b. its grammatical characteristics
- c. how it is pronounced”

This suggestion is generally useful for learners of English. However, the author would like to suggest some additional aspects to this concept to make it more suitable for the situation in Vietnam. They are *recognition ability* and *accessibility ability*.

By *recognition ability*, it means that if learners know a word, they must be able to recognize it in communication.

By *accessibility ability*, it means that if learners know a word, they must be able to resume it or access it whenever we need it.

2. Learners try not to learn new words in isolation. Try to learn collocations, idioms and expressions containing the words.

3. Learners should know what makes words be kept longer in mind.

What we think or experience can be recorded in the form of words by our brain. Words are stored in our brain in a way that there are links between their meaning and the form of their being (graphic, phonetic, visual, etc.). There are three basic types of these links: sight, sense and sound.

Sight link

This is the link set up when we see the thing the word refers to. For example when we see a table, the link between “the picture of a table” and “the meaning of the word table” in our brain is activated. This process makes the word “table” available at the moment we need it.

Sound linking

This is the link set up when we hear a particular sound or cluster of sounds which lead learners to a particular meaning a concept.

Meaning linking

This is the link set up when we feel or experience something abstract, inaudible and invisible. Words such as “cold”, “dangerous” or “mathematics” are accessed through links of this kind.

The stronger these links are, the longer learners can keep words in their mind and the better they can recognize and access words when they need. And, the more information they associate to a word, the stronger the links to the word are.

4. Effective methods of learning vocabulary should be applied as follows

- Learning vocabulary with objects

Using objects/pictures to teach or to learn vocabulary helps students make the sight link much stronger and develop their minds easily.

- Building up word meaning from its semantic features. This will strengthen the sense link inside the learner’s mind.
- Storytelling

“Stories are the way we store information in the brain. If teachers fill their students’ brains with miscellaneous facts and data without any connection, these things will be tossed and hopelessly lost. But stories help us to organize and remember information and tie the content together”

In addition, in the environment of storytelling, both teachers and students are emotionally connected by the nature of the story being told. This can help students develop a positive attitude toward the learning process, and also produces a sense of joy in language and words that is so often missing in the classroom setting. In this way, storytelling can motivate students during the learning in class. Research backs up the idea that “even students with low motivation and weak academic skills are more likely to listen, read, write and work hard in the context of storytelling” (U.S. Department of Education, 1986, 23). Any point that is made in a telling or any teaching that is done afterward is likely to be much more effective.

- Ways of learning vocabulary.
 - a. Making sentences
 - b. Using Word Trees
 - c. Using Bubble Networks
 - d. Using Tree Diagrams
 - e. Using Context.

- Word games

Various kinds of word games are available in books and especially on the Internet. Learners can benefit from these games in improving their amount of vocabulary.

3 CONCLUSION

When learning English, vocabulary is the most required skill. It has been considered as the basic for listening, speaking, reading and writing. So it is crucial for learners of English to learn as much vocabulary as possible in the most suitable and useful ways. Learners need to equip with vocabulary that helps them understand and communicate with others in English promptly. Finally, putting into words in English language is not easy, so learning vocabulary helps learners master English for their goals.

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